

Forming Child Character Through Socio-Cultural-Based Educational Games: A Case Study in Kindergarten in South-East Sulawesi

Anwar Hafid

Department of History, Faculty of Education,
University of Halu Oleo, Kendari 93232, South-east
Sulawesi, Indonesia

Ali Hadara

Department of History, Faculty of Education,
University of Halu Oleo, Kendari 93232, South-east
Sulawesi, Indonesia

Abstract:- The main problems faced by kindergarten teachers are: 1) less game tools, 2) limited fund source since most of the students come from low to middle families, 3) teachers have lack of ability to develop sociocultural-based games, and 4) lack of positive characters among kids and teenagers because they receive no cultural introduction since early stage. The research aimed to develop sociocultural based-educational games (*Alat Permainan Edukatif =APE*) with criteria: contain positive character values, easy to obtain, cheap, and appeal to children. Research result indicated that six kindergartens had developed each 7 types of APE applied in learning, namely: *Cugol, tinggoulo, tinggokasu, galaceng, sanadalemendaa, gacci, and Patolele*. Educationally, games developed contained positive character values (honesty, obedience to social rules, discipline, self-confidence, politeness, toughness, risk takers, intelligence, logical thinking, critical, creative and innovative, environmental awareness, respect the work and achievement of others, mutual assistance, and responsibility) as well as improve teachers' creativity.

Keywords:- Development, Educational Games, Sociocultural-Based, Positive Character, Teachers' Creativity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Early childhood education service is part of efforts to achieve the goals of education in Indonesia. One of early childhood education programs is kindergarten (*Taman Kanak-kanak/TK*) serving the need for education for children ages 5-6 years. It also helps in laying the foundations for attitude development and knowledge and skills needed by the children to adjust themselves with their environment.

Early childhood education is important since this is the golden age of growth; therefore, quality and good education in the aspect of materials, methods, and learning media are needed. In the aspect of material and media, the procurement of educational game tools could include both thus it is a must for teachers to bring sociocultural-based modern and contextual educational games.

Traditional games in some countries are developed in pre-school education. In Australia, Edwards and Meston (2009) actively promote traditional games at school and tribe groups. Some games can be played in traditional way and other have been modified thus there are some understanding on

basic skills and how to play the game by considering safety, easiness and fun.

Klim-Klimaszewska (2012) presented a method that could develop children creativity, such as: project method and board game. The methods create positive image and children creativity as well as give freedom to express for children.

The development of traditional games in kindergarten is a way for teachers and parents to prepare children through transition in entering the school. Teachers and parents should pay attention on the voice of their children in determining their future. In addition, a study by Margetts and Phatudi (2013) indicated that there are lots to do by government to increase awareness and accessibility of early childhood education to ensure the quality of provision in local level. The importance of children preparation through kindergarten for the development of social and emotional of children had indicated significance in lower grade in elementary school (Shala, 2013).

Research result in form of inventory of sociocultural-based games conducted by Anwar (2009) found 45 types of games from 5 groups in Kendari City, yet, not all of them are relevant to be developed for kindergarten children. A discussion with kindergarten teachers indicates criteria of games to be developed: 1) safe for kindergarten-age children, 2) contain educational elements that lead to the development of positive character, 3) based on sociocultural of the children, 4) materials are available in the surrounding environment, 5) easy to be made as well as cheap raw material, and 6) appeal to children to play.

Problems faced by kindergarten teachers are: 1) less games, 2) limited fund source, 3) teachers have less ability to develop sociocultural-based games, and 4) six kindergartens targeted by the program have different socio-culture and environment. Selection of the kindergarten was conducted by selecting 1 (one) kindergarten for each regency/city located in urban area, 1 (one) kindergarten located in coastal area, and 1 (one) kindergarten located in non-coastal suburban area.

Based on those problems, the urgent problem to be solved was the procurement of game tools containing positive character values since they are the main study materials for students. The lack of these tools can be solved by training on the development of local sociocultural-based educational games and technical guidance on the utilization.

The purpose of the study were: (1) to produce educational games that easy to obtain and foster positive character of the children as well as teachers' creativity, (2) to develop local culture so it will be more meaningful and able to nourish nationality and patriotism, and (3) to facilitate the procurement of game tools that can be developed to be traded in the market thus bring economic value for the kindergarten developed the games.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Play activities are tools for socialization. It is hoped that by playing, children could have opportunity to explore, to express their feeling, to be creative, and to have fun learning. In addition, the activities could help children to know themselves, with whom they live, and the environment where they live (Sujiono, 2009).

Learning by playing is fun activities for children. Semiawan (2002) gave example on mathematic learning in kindergarten through games. More effective games are those originated from sociocultural environment of students since they already have the basic skill to develop it. The games also could develop local culture that has positive character values.

Result of research by Li et al. (2016) found that kindergarten teachers in China were worried if their students are shy and unfriendly – it is prevailed in all cultural background. The finding indicates the importance of giving socialization instrument to children since early stage through games involving others so that children become skilled, have self-confidence, and are creative. Slavin (1986) viewed the need for early development of children potential through verbal language, reading, and writing. The same issue also stated by Aldogan (2016) that parents who have children with disabilities are faced with economic issue to provide appropriate education facilities for their children, including games that stimulate the development of the children. Empiric evidences indicate that children who are facilitated and given freedom to play since early stage shows better ability than those whom their movement are constrained and limited. Teachers should able to teach creative skills and creative thinking through direct learning by example.

Three external factors influencing neurodevelopment of early childhood, according to Finocchiaro (2016), as indicated in the context of this research, namely: the involvement of adult and home and school environments. Specific to school environment, it will depend on school leaders, skilled teachers, and the richness of material resources (educational toys).

Ation character education is interpreted as an education that develop cultural and character values of a nation for students so that they have those values and characters as theirs and apply them in their life as a member of a tribe and as religious, nationalist, productive, and creative citizen (Anwar, 2014). There are three ways to teach character to children: *First*, by changing the environment through arranging rules and consequences at school and home; *Second*, by giving knowledge on how to execute expected behavior to be applied in daily life; and *Third*, by conditioning the child's emotion

since emotion is 88% control in human life. By touching their emotion and giving the right information, those characters will stay in their life. According to Dewantara (1977) each teacher should able to give kindness or character learning.

Those values are implied in the culture of each ethnic group, oral and written. For Buton, Bugis, and Bajo ethnic groups, some of values developed have been written in form of prose, poem, song, and spells (Anwar, 2014). For Tolaki and Muna ethnic groups, positive characteristics are developed through oral traditions. Negative characteristics should be avoided in education process, whereas positive characteristics should be transformed to students and young generations of the nation both in learning/training and exemplary.

Learning in kindergarten is dominated more by moral reasoning to develop moral behavior. Thus, it is appropriate for teachers to understand moral reasoning to help their students in decision making and prepare them to make a decision. Lickona model is a new model developed to give direction for teachers who look for recommendation to promote moral behavior among students (Parson, 2001).

To date, tribes and governments have less emphasize on character education for children and teenagers; therefore, nationalism and patriotism erosion symptoms are occurred. For the last few years, government as well as tribes have acknowledge the importance of instilling character education in early stage that rooted in the national culture thus it becomes a habit since childhood and in turn, becomes a character that hard to change when teenagers or adults. In other words, children could apply positive characters value in their life.

III. RESEARC METHOD

This research was conducted at a kindergarten in Kendari City and Kolaka District which is a multi-ethnic population, each of which maintains traditional games in its life. The choice of location is intended to develop and adapt the culture of the community which tends to be forgotten by the younger generation, but on the other hand has positive character values. The research procedure was naturalistic, and the research subjects were community leaders, teachers and members of the local community. Data collection was carried out through observation, interviews, and discussions. Data validation techniques through: method triangulation, data source triangulation, and member checking. Data analysis techniques use domain analysis models, taxonomies, components, and analysis of cultural themes (Spradley, 2016).

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result achieved was that the six kindergartens had developed each 7 types of APE applied in learning, namely: *Cugol*, *tinggoulo*, *tinggokasu*, *galaceng*, *sanadale mendaa*, *gacci*, and *Patolele*.

Cugol is a traditional game of Mekongga Tribe and was developed to be APE by research team along with kindergarten teachers and IsrajuddinThamrin (parents of student). In this

activity, modification was conducted either in the materials or the rules.

Materials consisted of: (1) wooden board with size of 60 cm of length and 50 cm of width, (2) 12 woods with size of 7cm, (3) 2 goal posts made from net, (4) 2 wooden sticks with size of 15 cm, and (5) 2 balls in a size of marbles made from scrap paper (can be modified by using cap of mineral water bottle written with number 1-5 for white color and 6-10 for red color).

How to play: (1) started with a push competition, the loser will compile the pawns one by one, (2) the winner will kick first and then switch, (3) the kick is conducted in two ways: directly to the opponent's goalpost or ball is reflected in the edge of the field to the opponent's goalpost, (4) if the ball reflected to own goalpost, it is called suicide goal, (5) if there is a goal, players/viewers could scream *gool*, (6) kick can only be conducted in front of pawns of each player, (7) the game is in two rounds, each round is 17 minutes thus the game will last for 2 x 17 minutes, (8) entering the second round, new formation is arranged started from the winner, (9) if in 2x17 minutes the score is draw, 5 minutes additional time is given and if the result is still draw, penalties is conducted from one goal to another, and (10) player substitution is conducted, the losers replaced by new players.

Metinggo Ulo is one of traditional games of Tolaki, Mekongga, Muna and Bugis Tribes. Tools consisted of: coconut shell split into two and peeled and rope made of roots. How to play: it started with body balance exercise and then players hold the rope. Next, both legs are on the coconut shell with toes are clamping the rope and then walk as usual. In a race, it could be walking fast or run.

Metinggo Kasu is a tradition game of Tolaki and Mekongga Tribes. The game is conducted face to face. Tools: polished logs with size of 125 cm and diameter 10 cm. At the height of log of 50 cm, foot stand is given usesas footrest.

How to play: (1) started with body balance exercise, (2) *tinggokasu* is placed in front of a player, players' food step on the footrest one by one, (3) after players up on the logs, they have to maintain their balance so that they will not fall, and (4) slowly players walk by lifting their feet alternately.

Galaceng is a traditional game from Mekongga, Bugis and Bajo Tribes. In the beginning, a container with six pairs of hole in the left and right and one in each of end are made by punching holes in soil using wood and smooth the holes using heel.

Tools are consisted of: (1) wooden container with paired holes each 5 holes in the left and right. Big hole is made in each end of the right and left sides, (2) modification: in the research, the container was made from a polished wood with thickness of 3 cm and perforated, (3) grain stones were replaced with small shells with the same amount of 56, each hole contains 4 grains, and (4) modification: in the research, grain stones were replaced with small shells or tamarind seeds

available near the kindergartens thus it simplified children's understanding on their surrounding nature.

Players consist of two teams and each team consists of 1-2 persons. The game technique is started by a drawing, the winner starts the game by taking four grains in one hole in front of him/her and fill each of the next holes with one seed. If the seeds in hand are gone, the player takes all seeds in the last hole and continues the similar step. The game is over for the first team if the last grain found an empty hole. Next, the second team starts with the same steps.

Sandalemendaa is a traditional game of Tolaki Tribe. Tools: (1) log with size of 40 cm of length and 2 cm of thick, (2) rubber from used tired, and (3) nails and zinc for clips.

Each team consists of two or three players. The position will be in front, middle and back and touch other player's shoulders. Each pair of players will walk together and alternately. The winner is determined based on which pair of players reaches the finish line.

Gacci comes from Bugis Tribe. It means conducting a game using various shell seeds or tamarind seeds and *gacci* board with 40 cm of length and 3 cm of thick, (2) the game is a one on one game or two against two alternately.

The game is started with a drawing. The winning player starts the game. The first player takes 10 seeds and throws it on the board. The player puts his/her thumb on the board and pushes the seeds one by one until all the seeds out. The next player will do the same.

Patolele is a traditional game from Tolaki and Bugis Tribes. Tools used are sago stick. *Patolele* is made in two parts, long stick as a beater and small stick to be hit. The size of *Patolele* beater is 72 cm and the small one is 18 cm. Players consist of 3-5 persons.

How to play: (1) player stand and hold the beater and ready to hit the end of small *patolele* appear in the bottom of the hole, (2) small *patolele* is put above the hole and the beater is inserted in the hole, (3) small *patolele* is hit by the beater until it is out of the hole and other player (opponents) try to catch it before it hit the ground, (4) score system: first, if the opponent catch the stick with one hand the score will be 100 for the opponent; however, if he/she catches it with two hands the score is 50; second, if player hit small *patolele* and opponent cannot catch it, the calculation is based on the stick by calculating how many stick (multiples of 10) is the distance between the position where small *patolele* falls to the hole.

Currently, the development of kindergarten in rural and urban areas has required the development of sociocultural-based APE. 8 APEs developed could foster 13 positive character values. Honesty, obedience, and discipline contained in all games. The research result support a view that environmental impact in early life has influence on brain development. A baby who has good food, toys, and often asks to play has more mature brain function at the age of 12 years than those babies who receive no attention (Anwar and Ahmad, 2015).

Self-confidence showed in all games, such as able to throw the ball into the basket as many as possible in *Cugol* game and able to arrive in the finish line faster in *tingo* and *sandalemendaa* games. Self-confidence also showed by earning most points in *galaceng* and *patolele* games.

Politeness was indicated in *cugol* game especially when children sit, kick the ball, and speak. It was also indicated in *tinggo* and *sandalemendaa* games when players walk in their own line. *Galaceng* game also could develop politeness among children from the way they sit until how to distribute seeds in the holes. Politeness in *patolele* game was indicated when players hit the stick and measured the score. Rose and Nicholl (2006) stated that the requirement for effective learning is by presenting a supporting and fun environment similar to those in childhood through playing.

Logical, critical, creative and innovative thinking was indicated in determining strategy and tactics to kick the ball in *cogol* game and how to pick. Strategy to walk faster to the finish line was indicated in *tinggoulo*, *tinggokasu*, and *sandalemendaa* games. Strategies to choose holes in *galaceng* game, how to stick the seeds in *gacci* game or how to choose holes to be emptied and distribute seeds in other holes in *galaceng* game were also indicated those thinking. Empirically, those discoveries in science and technology are mostly resulted with the help of visualization (Wenger, 2014).

The attitude of risk takers was indicated when children climbed *tinggoulo*, *tinggokasu* where they might fall if they could not have balance. Awareness to environment was indicated when children chose seeds (in *galaceng* and *gacci* games) from old materials or materials available in their surrounding environment. In *Patolele* games, the materials used were also those available in their surrounding environment.

The attitude of respect the work and achievement of others could be developed through those 8 games developed. The attitude of accepting winning in a humble way and accepting defeat with courage and maintaining game tools made were the manifestation of respecting the work and achievement of others. This is the importance of social playing for children since they can learn from others and help others to develop friendship (Sujiono, 2009).

Mutual assistance attitude could be developed through *tinggoulo*, *tinggokasu*, and *sandalemendaa* games. In *tinggoulo* and *tinggokasu*, as well as *sandalemendaa* the attitude was indicated during the game. In these games players have risk to fall and when one player fell the others would immediately help their friends so they all will remain stands.

Responsibility attitude was indicated by children in *cugol* game where they have to kick all balls provided and tried to create goal in the opponent's goalpost. Responsibility was also indicated in *galaceng* game where children tried to choose the right hole to be emptied and distributed the seeds in the next hole, whereas in *gacci*, it was indicated when children tried to hit all seeds available to go to the goalpost.

Understanding the necessity of children characters development through the surrounding cultural foundation is important so that children do not lose their cultural identity that has positive character values. The findings are in line with the view of Dryden and Vos (2000) that in globalization era, Germany is increasingly Germany as well as French is increasingly French since they develop their culture as a basic in conquering the era and do not immersed in global culture.

Honesty value was indicated in *galaceng* game where player should stop when he/she reached an empty hole without having reprimanded. Mutual assistance value in *sandalemendaa* was indicated when one of friend is fell, others will help. accordance with Klim-Klimaszewska (2012) that provided a method that can develop kindergarten children activities and establish positive image of self as well as give freedom to express and to be creative.

The development of freedom to express and to be creative since early stage is in line with opinion of Yadav and Dixit (2017) stated that leadership development should go through learning of someone else life experience. The ability and behavior of kindergarten-age children is the result of accumulation of children experience with the environment (Hergenbahn and Olson, 2008). In this context, early stage learning through a game involving more than one person is a form of leadership learning.

Result of test in form of a race showed positive result, contextually. For example, when children played *magacci*, a question will emerge, "Is the fruits/tamarind seeds used in the game similar to those used by mother to cook fish"? Then, teacher will answer: "Yes, it is the same." As well as when teacher took the children out for a walk around their kindergarten to see tamarind tree firsthand, they would observe the tree and even tried to hug the tree. Then, they would look for tamarind fruit and peeled the skins to see the inside part and the seeds. Therefore, it would create character of environmental awareness since children would love their environment and love to plant trees. This activity created a positive side effect that was not included in the initial goal of the activity.

Children preparation through kindergarten in order to develop children's social and emotional especially when entering elementary school is important since empirically, as stated by Shala (2013), there was a significant relationship particularly in lower grade. The inculcation of nationalism in early childhood through APET is expected to prepare the future of the children to have identity in their local tribe as well as to have global vision to build the world together. Education that able to prepare human to have identity in their local tribe as well as to have global vision to build the world together is strongly needed in global culture (Anwar, 2009). However, it should be kept in mind that in the context of the research, students were come from various ethnical and religious backgrounds. According to Hall et al. (2008), teacher should be a model of respecting cultural differences and cultural limit that should be crossed by some students every day. The findings of this study are supported by the findings of Hafid

(2022) regarding pedagogical aspects in pokadulu culture in the Muna Tribe.

Theoretically and empirically, sociocultural-based development through “W theory” developed by Myon Woo Lee is proven to be effective to develop a new industrial country of South Korea (Sudjana, 2010). In the context of the research, effectiveness of the games development could have impact on the emergence of innovation from the surrounding tribes, in form of similar APE development to be marketed to the tribes and for students. In turn, this will bring side effect in the future when the children are grown up that they will have spirit to develop sociocultural environment and natural environment with economic, esthetic, and ethical values. The research finding could drive stakeholders of education to think about the substance of local content and self-development that currently designed and will be applied as part of curriculum from early childhood education program to middle school.

V. CONCLUSION

Instructively, games developed were easy to obtain and contained positive character values. The development of educational games was welcomed by parents and teachers since they could bring their old times back and they were favored by children. Cultural element that almost forgotten reappeared, and in fact, it could compete with other foreign cultures or imported games.

Games developed were economic, easy to obtain and cheap. They also could be developed to be sold in the market to give economic value for kindergarten that develops them. It is proven that games developed were generally made by teachers (all women) and parents. However, other tools, such as stones/seeds, were provided by teachers and their students.

Training and counseling are needed for teachers of kindergarten and other early childhood education programs (PAUD/ECEP) to develop games, either those originated from traditional culture or new motive that based on Indonesian culture and personality. Curriculum formulation for kindergarten and playground should consider sociocultural potential and the surrounding environment. Frequency of APET competition needs to be increased for PAUD student; thus, it will develop their patriotism. Broader APET development competition is needed by involving PAUD (kindergarten and playgroup) teachers so that they become more creative in developing learning materials in terms of their quality and quantity.

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